

DIGITAL LITERACY AND DIGITAL SELF-EFFICACY LEVELS AMONG PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS IN A STATE UNIVERSITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18360605>

ABSTRACT

Digital literacy and digital self-efficacy are essential 21st century skills that influence how pre-service teachers use technology for learning and future teaching. The main objective of the study was to determine the significant relationship between the levels of digital literacy and digital self-efficacy of Pre-Service Teachers of Bohol Island State University, Clarin Campus, Academic Year 2025-2026. Specifically, it aimed to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and academic program, the levels of digital literacy and digital self-efficacy of students, and the significant difference between the level of digital literacy and digital self-efficacy when grouped according to profile. The design used by the writers was the descriptive-correlational method with the aid of adopted questionnaires. The data gathered was treated statistically. Based on the findings, most of the respondents are between the ages of 21 and 22 years old, most of them are female, and are enrolled in the BTLEd-HE program. It was found that the respondents have a high level of digital literacy, which means students can effectively use digital tools and apply them in learning. Their level of digital self-efficacy was also high, which means students are confident in using technology for academic tasks. Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between the level of digital literacy and the level of digital self-efficacy of the students, $r(75)=0.49$, $p<.001$. It was concluded that students who are more confident in using digital tools also demonstrate stronger digital skills. It is recommended that the university continue to provide digital literacy training, integrate more hands-on digital activities, and foster a supportive digital learning environment. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies and explore additional factors such as motivation, teaching readiness, and access to digital resources.

Keywords: *Digital literacy, Digital self-efficacy, Pre-service teachers, State University*

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, mastering technology in education is very important since it prepares students for life in the complex technological world. It also encompasses skilled use of technology to interact, collaborate, perform research, and even generate new ideas, which are essential for succeeding not only in school but also later in life during one's career. As there is increasing dependence on technology for teaching and learning activities, fostering digital literacy has become critical in preparing students, especially teachers, for the 21st-century classroom.

Digital literacy is the ability to find, utilize, share, and create content using information and communication technologies and the internet. It includes the cognitive, technical, and social-emotional skills necessary to navigate and participate effectively in a digital environment, particularly in the context of teaching and learning. Digital literacy is important for education students because it provides them with the competencies to effectively utilize technology for learning, research, and communication, making them ready for a future where technology is part of teaching and learning. On the other hand, self-efficacy, or one's perception of their ability to achieve a task, improves academic outcomes through increased motivation, determination, and courage. Students who are confident in their capacities are able to take risks and showcase the best of their capabilities in digital as well as in traditional classrooms.

Davis (1989) developed the Technology Acceptance Model that explains why people start using new technology. Davis believed that people are more likely to use technology if they think it is useful and easy to use. This model encompasses that by using tools that are easy to understand and operate, students will also feel more confident using them. This would correspond with the concept of digital literacy and self-efficacy wherein students who are training to become teachers are more likely to use new digital tools if they believe these tools will improve their teaching and learning.

Moreover, the Digital Literacy Model of Alkali and Amichai-Hamburger (2004), highlights the significance of digital literacy as a complex set of cognitive, motoric, sociological, and emotional skills, including photo-visual, reproduction, branching, information, and socio-emotional literacies. It serves as a basis for appraising the digital skills needed in education systems. Using this model for analyzing the concepts of digital literacy and self-efficacy in technology use of teaching among pre-service teachers helps in understanding specific skill areas that impact their self-efficacy and preparedness in using technology in teaching. Additionally, the model's border socio-emotional literacy puts emphasis on appropriate digital communication which facilitates effective participatory teaching and learning in the classroom.

Furthermore, Matthew Gallagher (2012) Self-Efficacy Theory, describes an individual's belief in their capacity to perform specific tasks and achieve goals, shaped through mastery experiences, social modeling, and positive reinforcement. Gallagher

believed that success is not innate but can be developed when individuals are given supportive environments and opportunities to build their confidence. In the context of this study, self-efficacy theory supports the investigation of pre-service teachers' digital self-efficacy by highlighting the importance of empowering students through digital literacy experiences. It provides a foundational framework for understanding how confidence in using digital tools can influence learning outcomes and future teaching effectiveness among pre-service teachers at Bohol Island State University - Clarin Campus.

With the existing theories, the researchers found related studies that can elaborate more about digital literacy and relate it to the self-efficacy of the students.

Azhenov et al. (2023) explored the career decision-making readiness of students in higher education and found that those aged 21 to 22 were generally more prepared and capable of providing meaningful reflections about their career choices. The study revealed that this age group demonstrated greater self-awareness and confidence, allowing them to make more mature and goal-oriented academic decisions. Similarly, Mahinay et al. (2024) emphasized that students at the stage of young adulthood possess the maturity and practical understanding needed for effective classroom performance and professional growth.

In addition, Ceglédi et al. (2022) revealed that resilience plays a crucial role in maintaining motivation and commitment, particularly during academic challenges in digital or blended learning environments. Female students were often found to exhibit stronger perseverance and emotional adaptability, indicating that resilience supports both self-efficacy and long-term academic success in technology-mediated learning contexts. On the other hand, Dayanap et al. (2025) examined TVL graduates who pursued the Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education major in Home Economics and found that their prior exposure to technical-vocational subjects developed their confidence and preparedness in practical learning. The study revealed that these students were more motivated to continue in related programs due to their acquired skills and familiarity with the field. Similarly, Gabia (2025) found BTLEd program successfully enhanced students' competencies in both teaching and entrepreneurship.

According to Abiog (2022) that university students possessed basic digital skills such as online navigation and information searching, yet many still struggled with evaluating digital content critically. The study emphasized that students' confidence and familiarity with digital platforms greatly influenced their literacy performance. Similarly, Yeh (2022) discovered that students in flipped classrooms learned more effectively when digital activities encouraged active participation, collaboration, and repeated practice, showing that engagement is a key element of digital learning.

Moreover, Prashar et al. (2024) revealed that teaching students about plagiarism and the ethical use of digital information increased their academic honesty and responsibility, highlighting the importance of digital ethics as part of digital literacy. Supporting this, Alua et al. (2023) found that using tools like Turnitin, combined with proper teacher guidance, helped improve students' writing behavior, though they stressed that technology alone cannot replace proper instruction on responsible online practices.

In addition, Safitri and Arsyad (2022) found that while most university students understood that plagiarism is an unethical practice, many still lacked proper knowledge of citation and referencing techniques.

Olabiya et al. (2025) discovered that digital resources can greatly improve literacy results, especially in areas such as reading comprehension, vocabulary development, and writing skills. Nonetheless, the level of their effectiveness differs based on various factors, including teacher training, availability of technology, and socio-economic conditions. Learners with more regular access to digital educational tools and support from well-prepared teachers showed more significant advancements in their literacy abilities. In addition, Gitadewi (2024) reported that integrating problem-based learning strategies significantly improved students' digital literacy and critical-thinking skills, as learners became more creative and confident when solving real-world problems through digital means. Likewise, Gutiérrez-Aguilar et al. (2024) discovered that university students who actively participated in online and offline activities demonstrated higher levels of digital citizenship. Their research revealed that skills related to inquiry, searching, and critical questioning were stronger predictors of responsible digital behavior than simply having access to technology. Moreover, Gu et al. (2023) also discovered that students used digital platforms not only for academic tasks but also for creative and cultural expression, indicating that digital literacy extends beyond technical ability to include communication and identity.

O'Toole et al. (2024) emphasized that digital citizenship goes beyond technical skills, highlighting the importance of values, cultural awareness, and responsible online behavior in creating a positive digital environment. Their study revealed that students who were guided to reflect on ethical and cultural aspects of technology use became more respectful and mindful in their digital interactions. Similarly, Althibyani and Al-Zahrani (2023) discovered that students with stronger digital knowledge, positive beliefs, and well-developed digital citizenship skills were more capable of preventing cybercrimes and promoting online safety. In the Philippine context, Cleofas (2025) found that young people with higher digital competence were more likely to participate in online civic activities and act responsibly in digital spaces, showing that digital literacy contributes to building good digital citizens.

According to Ungerer (2016) digital curation is a vital skill in higher education, as it enables students to critically select, organize, and evaluate online information for meaningful learning. The study revealed that integrating digital curation into academic activities helps learners become more discerning and responsible users of digital content. Similarly, Putri et al. (2025) found that improving students' digital literacy through technology enhances their ability to seek, assess, and apply information effectively. Their findings showed that students who actively practice information-seeking skills develop greater independence and confidence in using digital tools for learning. Moreover, Mihailidis (2015) highlighted that when students learn how to curate digital content such as selecting, organizing, and sharing information thoughtfully, they develop stronger critical and reflective thinking skills.

In the study of, Hsu et al. (2021) showed that students who understood digital responsibility were more engaged in positive online actions such as volunteering and advocacy campaigns. Likewise, Hehir et al. (2021) revealed that using digital resources effectively during remote learning helped students feel more connected with their peers and teachers. Their study emphasized that digital tools, when used responsibly, can strengthen collaboration, engagement, and a sense of belonging in virtual learning environments. Similarly, Castillo De Mesa and Gómez Jacinto (2022) found that strong digital skills were linked to better social connections and greater tolerance toward others, emphasizing that digital literacy also promotes empathy and inclusiveness.

Cojocariu and Boghian (2024) found digital creativity as an essential component of higher education, as it allows students to use technology in innovative and meaningful ways. Their study revealed that fostering digital creativity helps learners express ideas more effectively, engage deeply in learning tasks, and adapt to the demands of a technology-driven environment. According to Manca and Ranieri (2017) social media, when guided by digitally competent teachers, can enhance learning and collaboration, reinforcing the role of educators in modeling responsible digital practices. Herawan et al. (2023) found that students who used digital tools creatively achieved higher learning outcomes and developed better critical thinking, suggesting that digital literacy encourages both creativity and deep learning.

Wang and Wu (2022) found that online cooperative learning significantly improved students' problem-solving abilities and overall learning satisfaction, as collaboration encouraged critical thinking and mutual support among peers. Similarly, Jiang et al. (2023) highlighted that online collaborative problem-solving has become an essential educational approach, promoting communication, creativity, and teamwork in digital learning environments. In addition, Corrales and Tenorio (2024) revealed that engaging in online collaboration helped students strengthen their cognitive and analytical skills, particularly in social studies, by fostering deeper discussions and shared learning experiences. Likewise, Kwiatkowska and Wiśniewska (2022) reported that digital and metacognitive skills were strong predictors of effective online collaboration, while Mena-Guacas et al. (2023) discovered that students with stronger digital skills were more willing to cooperate and share knowledge with others. Furthermore, Smith and Storrs (2023) found that students recognized the importance of developing digital literacies and social media skills to effectively engage in academic and collaborative work, showing that awareness of what they need to learn helps them become more responsible and capable digital learners. However, unequal access to digital tools and internet connectivity remained a challenge that affected overall literacy performance.

Malabanan et al. (2022) examined pre-service teachers' readiness for online learning and their 21st-century pedagogical skills, revealing that those who possessed higher levels of digital literacy and confidence were better prepared to manage online classes and integrate technology into their teaching. In addition, Olur and Ocaik (2021) developed a digital literacy self-efficacy scale and found that students with greater confidence in their digital abilities were more likely to engage positively with technology and adapt to new digital tools. In the same way, Pumptow and Brahm (2021) highlighted that students' digital media self-efficacy plays a crucial role in their success in higher

education, as those who believe in their digital skills tend to use technology more effectively and participate more actively in online learning environments.

According to Steinert and Dennis (2022) emotions play a key role in digital well-being, showing that positive emotional engagement on social media helps users maintain balance and confidence in online spaces. In addition, Ibrahim et al. (2024) discovered that digital literacy and self-regulation help reduce academic stress by strengthening emotional intelligence, suggesting that being emotionally aware and digitally skilled allows students to manage challenges more effectively in both academic and digital environments. Moreover, Doménech et al. (2024) explored the connection between emotion regulation, self-efficacy, and personality traits such as emotional stability and extraversion among adolescents. Their findings revealed that individuals who could manage their emotions well-tended to have stronger self-belief and confidence when facing new challenges, including those related to digital tasks and online learning.

Bacarrisas (2023) focuses on self-efficacy in information literacy, not specifically digital literacy. It finds that high self-efficacy in information literacy significantly influences college students' research academic skills, indicating confidence in conducting effective research and using information effectively. In addition, Daniel (2014) found that learners with low self-efficacy in information literacy tended to use library resources less often but showed a stronger willingness to learn how to use them. This suggests that even students with limited confidence can develop their skills when given proper guidance and support. Moreover, Hatlevik et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between students' ICT self-efficacy and their computer and information literacy. The results showed that students with higher confidence in their technological abilities were more effective in gathering, evaluating, and applying digital information.

In the study of Aldosari et al. (2020) found that students with higher internet self-efficacy demonstrated stronger awareness and practice of digital citizenship standards, showing that confidence in using online tools encourages more responsible digital behavior. In the same way, Scheel et al. (2022) discovered that digital competence, self-organization, and independent learning skills greatly influence students' acceptance of digital learning, suggesting that confident and organized learners are more open to using digital platforms effectively. Likewise, Ma et al. (2025) revealed that digital safety competence positively affects students' cognitive skills, AI self-efficacy, and character development, emphasizing that being digitally safe and aware builds both intelligence and integrity in online environments. Moreover, Martens and Hobbs (2015) highlighted the importance of media literacy in promoting civic engagement in the digital age. Their study revealed that students who are more media literate are not only better at critically evaluating online information but are also more likely to participate in responsible digital citizenship activities.

Ansari (2022) examined the self-efficacy for online learning among both young and older university students in Sindh, revealing that confidence in one's ability to use digital tools significantly affects learning engagement and success. This study found that younger students generally demonstrated higher digital self-efficacy due to more frequent exposure to technology, while older students relied on self-regulation and motivation to

overcome technological challenges. In addition, O'Neill et al. (2024) found that self-efficacy significantly influences older adults' perspectives on technology use, impacting their digital literacy and adoption rates. Higher self-efficacy correlates with increased confidence and motivation, facilitating greater engagement and reducing technological inequalities among older individuals.

Javier-Aliaga et al. (2024) explored the relationship between academic self-efficacy and digital competence among university students and found that those with higher confidence in their academic abilities also demonstrated stronger digital skills. The study showed that believing in one's ability to learn effectively contributes to better use of digital tools and resources for academic tasks. Similarly, Sarva et al. (2023) examined the development of digital competences among education students and revealed that both students and stakeholders recognized the importance of integrating digital skills into teacher education. Their findings highlighted that continuous digital training helps future educators adapt to technological changes and enhance their teaching effectiveness.

Lafifa and Rosana (2023) examined the digital literacy levels of junior high school students and found no significant difference between male and female students. Their results showed that both genders displayed comparable abilities in using digital tools and navigating online information, suggesting that access to technology and learning opportunities has become more balanced. Similarly, A and Sinha (2022) investigated the link between digital literacy and age among university students and revealed that age did not significantly affect students' digital competence. The study emphasized that exposure to digital learning environments across different age groups has led to more uniform digital skills. In addition, Jan (2018) reported that students showed no significant difference in digital literacy across school levels or academic programs, indicating that integration of technology in education has become consistent across various learning settings, allowing students from different programs to develop similar digital abilities.

The research conducted by Prior et al. (2016) on the connection between attitudes, digital literacy, self-efficacy, and online learning behavior provides direct support for studies examining digital literacy and self-efficacy levels in multiple ways. Their results reveal a positive relationship between higher levels of digital literacy and increased self-efficacy in online learning contexts. This causal relationship is significant because it demonstrates that improved digital competencies directly lead to greater confidence in leveraging technology for educational purposes. In addition, the study underscores the impact that increased self-efficacy has on student engagement, indicating that students with higher confidence are more inclined to actively take part in online learning activities, engage with both peers and instructors, and effectively use learning management systems.

In addition, Ervianti and Pratama (2024) found that the degree of self-efficacy regarding computer skills significantly influences students' digital literacy. Students play a crucial role in three key areas: (1) taking direct responsibility for digital literacy as a means of facilitating lectures, (2) acting as a support system during lectures, and (3) serving as a valuable reference for their peers, which aids in accessing information, data, and learning theories. Consequently, a person's proficiency in utilizing digital literacy

correlates positively with their level of self-efficacy in computer skills. Furthermore, Lugnasin and Espinosa (2024) found that self-efficacy significantly influences students' engagement, aiding in their personal growth and encouraging active involvement in the learning process.

Based on the conducted preliminary survey result, the majority of the students in Bohol Island State University - Clarin Campus have difficulty in preparing and using information and communication technologies such as projectors, laptops, computers, and others, to meet their needs. In addition, only 21 students out of 95 students are capable in fixing common technical issues. In Bohol Island State University (BISU), one of its missions is to provide quality higher education, especially in the professional and technological fields, where the College of Teacher Education has a big role in molding and nurturing students majoring in education to be professionally equipped and digitally literate. Thesis writers know that despite the growing importance of digital literacy in education, there is limited research on the levels of digital literacy and digital self-efficacy among students, specifically for pre-service teachers.

The researchers focused on the levels of digital literacy and self-efficacy levels of the College of Teacher Education students of Bohol Island State University (BISU) - Clarin Campus. As the researchers identified the gaps, they evaluated the levels of digital literacy of the students and their digital self-efficacy levels. By evaluating how digital literacy affects students' digital self-efficacy, this study sought the potential benefits or improvements among students' digital literacy skills and preparedness for teaching through conducting a seminar training program that would help students to become more capable in using digital tools, especially in information and communication technologies.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to determine the levels of digital literacy and digital self-efficacy of Pre-Service Teachers of Bohol Island State University (BISU) - Clarin Campus Academic Year 2025-2026.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of age, gender, and academic program?
2. What is the level of digital literacy of students in terms of communication, copyright, critical thinking, character, citizenship, curation, connectedness, creativity, and collaboration?
3. What is the level of digital self-efficacy of students in terms of cooperation in digital environments, emotion management in digital environments, information management in digital environments, and awareness in digital environments?
4. Is there a significant difference in the student level of digital literacy and the level of digital self-efficacy when grouped according to profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the levels of digital literacy of students and their levels of digital self-efficacy?

METHODOLOGY

Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationship between digital literacy and digital self-efficacy levels among students in the College of Teacher Education at Bohol Island State University (BISU) - Clarin Campus Academic Year 2025-2026. A survey questionnaire was used to gather data on students' demographic profiles, digital literacy, and digital self-efficacy. The sample was selected using stratified random sampling to ensure representation across different programs.

Environment

The study was conducted at Bohol Island State University (BISU) - Clarin Campus, Poblacion Norte, Clarin, Bohol, during the Academic Year 2025-2026, specifically within the College of Teacher Education. Bohol Island State University (BISU) - Clarin Campus offers education programs such as Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics, Bachelor of Elementary Education, and Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education Major in Home Economics, with a total population of 95 students, where they use some digital tools.

Respondents

The respondents of this study are the fourth-year pre-service teachers, specifically the eighteen (18) Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics, twenty-three (23) Bachelor of Elementary Education, and thirty-six (36) Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education Major in Home Economics, determined using stratified random sampling and proportional allocation. The only criterion for the respondents of this study is that they are fourth-year College students enrolled in the College of Teacher Education at Bohol Island State University (BISU) - Clarin Campus during the Academic Year 2025-2026, as they were future educators who would use digital tools in their teaching.

Instrument

A survey questionnaire was used in gathering the data. The questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part of the questionnaire was the profile of the respondents in terms of their gender, age, and program. The second part of the questionnaire was an adopted Digital Literacy Scale (DLS) developed by Amin et al. (2021) and has thirty-six (36) items and nine (9) factors (7 items for Communication, 4 items for Copyright, 3 items for Critical Thinking, 3 items for Character, 4 items for Citizenship, 3 items for Curation, 5 items for Connectedness, 4 items for Creativity, and 3 items for Collaboration) that would determine the level of digital literacy of College of Teacher Education students of Bohol Island State University (BISU) - Clarin. The Digital Literacy Scale served as valid and reliable, with a Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin 0.886, total variance of 62.87%, Cronbach Alpha 0.894, and the goodness of fit 0.924. The questionnaire was interpreted through a 4-point Likert Scaling: 4 –

Strongly Agree (Strong and consistent digital competencies across all dimensions), 3 – Agree (Good digital literacy, but with room for development in certain areas), 2 – Disagree (Struggles with several aspects of digital literacy; needs structured support), and 1 – Strongly Disagree (Severely limited digital literacy; requires foundational skill-building).

The third part of the questionnaire was an adopted Digital Literacy Self-Efficacy Scale developed by Olur & Ocaik (2021) and has twenty-one (21) items and four (4) sub-dimensions (7 items for Cooperation in Digital Environments, 5 items for Emotion Management in Digital Environments, 5 items for Information Management in Digital Environments, and 4 items for Awareness in Digital Environments) that would determine the level of digital self-efficacy of College of Teacher Education students of Bohol Island State University (BISU) - Clarin. The Digital Literacy Self-Efficacy Scale served as a valid and reliable scale with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.994. Exploratory and Confirmatory Factor Analysis were also used during the scale development process. The questionnaire was interpreted through a 4-point Likert Scaling: 4 – Strongly Agree (Feels very confident using a wide range of digital tools and solving tech-related issues), 3 – Agree (Generally confident, but may avoid or hesitate with unfamiliar digital challenges), 2 – Disagree (Often lacks confidence and may struggle with basic to intermediate digital tasks), and 1 – Strongly Disagree (Lacks basic digital confidence and may be hesitant or resistant to using technology). In answering the questionnaire, the respondents were asked to place their responses by marking the table that corresponds to their judgment.

Procedure

In gathering the data, the researchers sent a letter of request to the Campus Director to conduct the study and asked for consent to get the list of the fourth-year College of Teacher Education students of the university for the Academic Year 2025-2026 from the Registrar's Office. Once approved, the research questionnaire was distributed personally to the respondents using a descriptive-correlational survey questionnaire. The descriptive-correlational survey questionnaire included clear, simple instructions so that respondents could quickly respond to the questions. The completed descriptive-correlational survey questionnaires were collected on the same day the questionnaires were being handled. After gathering the data, the researchers tallied, tabulated, and interpreted the results. The results are used as the basis for conclusions and recommendations.

Data Analysis

The data were subjected to the following statistical treatments. The simple percentage was utilized to determine the frequency of the responses of the profile of the respondents.

The weighted mean was used to determine the level of digital literacy of the students. 3.51 – 4.00 corresponds Highly Literate (HL), 2.51 – 3.50 corresponds Moderately Literate (ML), 1.51 – 2.50 corresponds Slightly Literate (SL), and 1.00 – 1.50 corresponds Least Literate (LL).

The weighted mean was used to determine the level of digital self-efficacy of the students. 3.51 – 4.00 corresponds Very High (VH), 2.51 – 3.50 corresponds High (H), 1.51 – 2.50 corresponds Moderate (M), and 1.00 – 1.50 corresponds Low (L).

The Chi-square was used to determine the significant difference in the student level of digital literacy and the level of digital self-efficacy when grouped according to their profile.

The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to determine the significant relationship between the level of digital literacy and the level of students' digital self-efficacy in using technology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents in detail the findings, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data. The gathered data are presented in tables. It generally covers the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and academic program, students' level of digital literacy, and their level of digital self-efficacy when grouped according to profile, and the significant relationship between the levels of digital literacy and digital self-efficacy.

1. Profile of the Respondents as to their Age, Gender, and Academic Program

As the intervening variables, age, gender, and program of the respondents are being considered to determine their contributions and to assess their significant difference from the other variables of the study.

Table 1
Respondents' Profile
n= 77

Age	Counts	Percentage (%)
20	3	3.9
21	48	62.3
22	20	26.0
23	2	2.6
24	4	5.2
Gender	Counts	Percentage (%)
Male	14	18.2
Female	63	81.8
Academic Program	Counts	Percentage (%)
BSED-MATH	18	23.4
BEED	23	29.9
BTLED-HE	36	46.8
Total	77	100

Statistical Tool: Simple Percentage

Table 1 reveals the percentage results of the age, gender, and academic program. Most of the respondents are 21 years old, comprising 48 or 62.3% of the population. Age 22 years old compose of 20 or 26% of the population. Moreover, there were only 2 respondents or 2.6% of the population who were aged 23 years old. This means that the majority of the respondents were aged 21 to 22 years old, which reflects a maturity, readiness, and ability to give meaningful responses of individuals towards participation in this study. This is because students at this age are already in their senior year, where they have been sufficiently exposed to academic tasks, research activities, and digital learning environments, allowing them to provide informed and meaningful responses to the study. It corresponds to the studies of Azhenov et al. (2023) and Mahinay et al. (2024) that students ages 21-22 are developmentally prepared and able to provide meaningful responses about their preparedness.

As to the gender of the respondents, it reveals that 18.2% of the respondents are male, while 81.8% of the respondents are female. This means that the majority of the respondents are female. This is because female students are more likely to enroll in education-related programs at BISU–Clarín Campus, as teaching is traditionally viewed as a profession that attracts more female learners due to its nurturing and service-oriented nature. This aligns with the study of Ceglédi et al. (2022) who found that female students have become the majority in many higher-education fields and tend to exhibit stronger persistence behaviors, even when coming from less favorable social backgrounds.

As to the academic program of the respondents, it reveals that 46.8% of the respondents are from the Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education Major in Home Economics, and 29.9% are from Bachelor of Elementary Education, while 23.4% are from Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics. This means that the majority of the respondents are BTLEd-HE. This distribution suggests that students with prior exposure to technical-vocational subjects tend to continue related programs in college, as these programs align with their skills, interests, and future career opportunities. It corresponds to the study of Dayanap et al. (2025) found that many Senior High School graduates from Technical-Vocational-Livelihood tracks chose this program because of their prior exposure to technical and practical skills during high school. Also, the study emphasized that students were motivated to enroll in BTLEd–HE not only due to familiarity with the specialization but also because of its promising career pathways in teaching and entrepreneurship. Similarly, Gabia (2025) evaluated the curriculum and instructional design of the BTLEd major in Home Economics and found that its competency-based structure and alignment with industry standards made it one of the most preferred programs among education students in the Philippines.

2. Students' Level of Digital Literacy Skills

As the dependent variable of the study, the students' digital literacy is being considered to determine how effectively they apply their digital knowledge and skills in various online contexts and to assess how their ability to use technology responsibly and creatively supports their learning performance and professional readiness

Table 2
Level of Digital Literacy
n= 77

Components	Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Communication	1. I can easily read online contents from screen.	3.71	0.48	Highly Literate
	2. I prefer to take prints of online reading materials for better reading.	3.42	0.69	Moderately Literate
	3. I can type quickly using both hands.	3.19	0.76	Moderately Literate
	4. I know how to write formal emails.	3.04	0.57	Moderately Literate
	5. I am well-aware about email sending and formatting options.	3.12	0.65	Moderately Literate
	6. I interact through online audio-video calls.	3.22	0.64	Moderately Literate
	7. Online listening through headphones and speakers is troublesome for me.	2.35	0.79	Slightly Literate
	Composite	3.15	0.76	Moderately Literate
Copyright	8. I know the online plagiarism policy of my institute.	3.39	0.59	Moderately Literate
	9. I know the consequences of using copyright work online without permission.	3.64	0.51	Highly Literate
	10. I give acknowledgement/reference in my online work while using collusion (copyright from fellow students).	3.31	0.59	Moderately Literate
	11. I use Turnitin or other similar software to check and avoid unintentional plagiarism.	2.90	0.66	Moderately Literate
	Composite	3.31	0.64	Moderately Literate
Critical Thinking	12. My university assigns me online activities relating to real life problems.	3.12	0.73	Moderately Literate
	13. I am able to find different pieces of information online and put them together to solve a problem.	3.22	0.66	Moderately Literate
	14. I have an online reflective journal to write.	2.60	0.73	Moderately Literate
	Composite	2.98	0.75	Moderately Literate
Character	15. In the online world, I do not use and share others' personal information, pictures, conversation etc. without their consent.	3.47	0.60	Moderately Literate
	16. I avoid posting negative online comments and poking in others' discussion and chatting.	3.62	0.54	Highly Literate
	17. I remain neutral and tolerant during online discussions.	3.31	0.59	Moderately Literate
	Composite	3.47	0.59	Moderately Literate
Citizenship	18. I can communicate with others in a respectable way while using technology.	3.66	0.50	Highly Literate
	19. I know the consequences for violating cyber laws in the digital world.	3.70	0.49	Highly Literate
	20. I accept the consequences for violating cyber laws in the digital world.	3.57	0.50	Highly Literate
	21. I respect the cultural differences in the online world and respond accordingly.	3.71	0.45	Highly Literate
	Composite	3.66	0.49	Highly Literate
Curation	22. I search for material from renowned websites.	3.32	0.52	Moderately Literate
	23. I try to add value to the existing pieces of information available online.	3.18	0.56	Moderately Literate
	24. I play my part in adding to and updating online information.	3.13	0.59	Moderately Literate
	Composite	3.21	0.56	Moderately Literate
Connectedness	25. I am involved in different online communities for volunteer work.	2.55	0.66	Moderately Literate
	26. I participate in different online projects at national level.	2.19	0.63	Slightly Literate
	27. I actively take interest in different online campaigns for community development.	2.64	0.74	Moderately Literate
	28. I actively participate in online polls/surveys.	2.91	0.71	Moderately Literate
	29. I encourage and help my community to post their problems and issues on social media to get attention.	2.29	0.89	Slightly Literate
	Composite	2.51	0.77	Moderately Literate
Creativity	30. I write online blogs giving new ideas and perspectives.	2.17	0.71	Slightly Literate
	31. I like to post new information on my social media account(s).	2.61	0.85	Moderately Literate
	32. I develop my own videos and post them online.	2.61	0.83	Moderately Literate
	33. I have creative ideas but do not know how to use them online.	2.78	0.68	Moderately Literate
	Composite	2.54	0.80	Moderately Literate
Collaboration	34. In the online world, I work with others in groups.	2.73	0.79	Moderately Literate
	35. Working in online groups helps me to learn from others.	3.04	0.66	Moderately Literate
	36. I work online with my peers to find solutions to the problems.	3.05	0.65	Moderately Literate
	Composite	2.94	0.71	Moderately Literate
Overall Mean		3.07	0.79	Moderately Literate

Statistical Tool: Weighted Mean

Legend: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA), 2.51-3.50 Agree (A), 1.51-2.50 Disagree (D), 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2 shows the students' level of digital literacy in terms of communication, copyright, critical thinking, character, citizenship, curation, connectedness, creativity, and collaboration. Among all the seven (7) statements in communication, item 1 got the highest ($M=3.71$, $SD=0.48$) which described as moderately literate, showing that students are comfortable navigating and reading online materials. As noted by Abiog (2022) that university students in the Philippines display a positive attitudes toward reading and viewing online materials, which indicates a growing level of digital familiarity and comfort among learners in higher education.

On the other hand, item 7 receives the lowest ($M=2.35$, $SD=0.76$), which is described as slightly literate. This means that most students do not find difficulty in using audio devices during online activities. This aligns in the study of Yeh (2022) that students expressed high satisfaction and comfort in learning through audio-visual materials, demonstrating ease in listening and viewing media in digital learning settings.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.15$, $SD=0.76$) described as moderately literate of digital literacy in communication. This suggests that students generally possessed the necessary communication skills for digital interaction and information exchange such as reading online content, typing efficiently, emailing, and participating in audio-video calls without difficulty. This is because they are frequently exposed to online reading materials, emails, and virtual meetings, which helps them become comfortable with digital communication tools. Moreover, this result aligned with the Digital Literacy Model of Alkali and Amichai-Hamburger (2004), which highlighted that digital literacy involves cognitive, social, and emotional skills that allow individuals to communicate effectively in digital spaces. The students' ability to read, write, and engage in online communication reflects these literacies, showing that they are not only technically capable but also socially and emotionally ready to use technology for meaningful communication and learning.

In addition, among all the four (4) statements in copyright, item 9 got the highest ($M=3.64$, $SD=0.51$) which described as highly literate, showing that students have a strong understanding of copyright responsibility and recognize the importance of respecting intellectual property in the digital environment. This aligned with the study of Prashar et al. (2024) which emphasized that students with greater awareness of copyright and plagiarism consequences tend to practice academic honesty more consistently.

Whereas, the item 11 got the lowest ($M=2.90$, $SD=0.66$) which described as moderately literate, showing that while students know the importance of avoiding plagiarism, not all of the students actively use plagiarism-detection tools. According to Alua et al. (2023), many students are positively disposed to the idea of plagiarism detection but lack knowledge about the software's availability or how to interpret similarity reports.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.31$, $SD=0.64$) is described as moderately literate of digital literacy in terms of awareness and adherence to copyright policies and plagiarism prevention measures within their academic environment. This suggested that most students demonstrate awareness and responsible behavior toward copyright use

and plagiarism. This may be attributed to the university's emphasis on academic honesty and research requirements, which regularly remind students of proper citation practices. This aligns with the study of Safitri and Arsyad (2022), which emphasized that students who recognize the importance of avoiding plagiarism and citing sources properly are more capable of practicing ethical academic writing. Moreover, according to the theory of Alkali and Amichai-Hamburger (2004) in the Digital Literacy Model, digital literacy involves not only technical but also ethical and cognitive skills essential for responsible online engagement.

Moreover, among all three (3) statements in critical thinking, item 13 got the highest ($M=3.22$, $SD=0.66$), which was described as moderately literate, showing that students are capable of gathering and synthesizing online information to solve tasks. It is indicated by Olabiyi et al. (2025) that digital resources enhanced students' literacy and problem-solving skills when supported by proper access and guidance. This exposure to digital tools helps students effectively analyze and apply information in solving tasks.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=2.98$, $SD=0.75$) is described as moderately literate in critical thinking in digital learning contexts. This is because they are often assigned online tasks that require searching, comparing, and organizing information. According to Gitadewi (2024), integrating digital literacy strengthens students' critical thinking and confidence in using digital tools for complex learning activities. It implies that fostering structured, reflective, and problem-solving digital experiences can further enhance students' overall critical thinking skills.

Furthermore, among all three (3) statements in character, item 16 got the highest ($M=3.62$, $SD=0.54$), which was described as highly literate, showing that most students practice respect and responsibility in online behavior. According to Gutiérrez-Aguilar et al. (2024), students with more advanced digital skills tend to display more robust digital citizenship behaviors, such as respectful online communication and adherence to appropriate norms.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.47$, $SD=0.59$) described as moderately literate of digital literacy in terms of character that students respected others' privacy, refrained from posting negative comments or intruding into discussions, and maintained a neutral and tolerant attitude during online interactions, demonstrating good character traits such as respect, empathy, and digital etiquette in online activities. This is because they are aware of proper online etiquette and the consequences of inappropriate behavior, which encourages them to respect others' privacy and opinions in digital spaces. As noted by Gu et al. (2023), students who actively use digital tools and engage with social media in morally aware ways tend to exhibit stronger digital citizenship and literacy practices.

Additionally, among all four (4) statements in citizenship, item 21 got the highest ($M=3.71$, $SD=0.45$), which was described as highly literate, showing that students demonstrate a high level of respect toward cultural differences and maintain responsible communication online. This aligns with the study of O'Toole et al. (2024), which emphasized that learners who engage meaningfully in online environments tend to

develop stronger cultural sensitivity and digital respect, fostering positive and inclusive digital interactions.

Whereas, item 20 got the lowest ($M=3.57$, $SD=0.50$) but was still described as highly literate, showing that although students acknowledge the importance of following cyber laws, some may have limited awareness of the consequences of online violations. According to Althibyani and Al-Zahrani (2023), students' understanding of digital laws and ethical use of technology increases when they are continuously exposed to digital responsibility education, which reinforces accountability and lawful online behavior.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.66$, $SD=0.49$) is described as highly literate of digital literacy in terms of citizenship. The results revealed that students possessed excellent online communication skills, were well-informed about cyber laws and consequences, and demonstrated respect for cultural differences in the digital environment, showing a strong commitment to ethical and responsible online behavior. This can be explained by their awareness of cyber laws, cultural sensitivity, and responsible online communication, which are reinforced through academic discussions and institutional policies. In line of the study of Cleofas (2025) found that undergraduates with high digital citizenship demonstrated an ethical online engagement and civic responsibility.

Moreover, among all three (3) statements in curation, item 22 obtained the highest ($M=3.32$, $SD=0.52$), which was described as moderately literate, indicating that students often search for learning materials from credible and renowned websites. This shows that they are careful and responsible in selecting trustworthy online sources to support their academic tasks. This aligns with the study of Ungerer (2016) that emphasized students who develop curation skills demonstrate stronger information literacy and are better equipped for the abundance of online content. Moreover, Putri et al. (2025) found that students with strong information-seeking behaviors such as searching, verifying, and using information from reputable online sources exhibited higher overall digital literacy.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.21$, $SD=0.56$) is described as moderately literate of digital literacy in terms of curation. The results revealed that students are competent in curating online information by searching, organizing, and contributing to reliable digital materials. This is because they are accustomed to searching for credible sources for schoolwork, although they may have limited opportunities to actively contribute to updating or improving online content. According to Mihailidis (2015), curating content, such as sourcing, organizing, and analyzing, improves students' media analysis, narrative clarity, and critical literacy.

Further, among all five (5) statements in connectedness, item 28 got the highest ($M=2.91$, $SD=0.71$), which was described as moderately literate, indicating that students participated in online polls and campaigns, showing their willingness to participate in digital communities. As noted by Hsu et al. (2021) that a sense of civic responsibility and exposure to online learning or expression strongly influence students' willingness to engage in civic activities online.

Whereas, the item 26 got the lowest ($M=2.19$, $SD=0.63$) which described as slightly literate, showing that students are less engaged in broader, large-scale digital initiatives, possibly due to limited access, lack of confidence, of fewer opportunities for national collaboration. In line of the study of Hehir et al. (2021) found that students often experience challenges in maintaining engagement in large-scale digital communities due to the lack of direct social interaction and institutional guidance.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=2.51$, $SD=0.77$) described as moderately literate of digital literacy in terms of connectedness. This result suggested that students are aware of online participation but may still lack strong engagement in more impactful or large-scale digital collaboration. This may be due to limited exposure to national or community-based digital projects and fewer opportunities for civic participation through online platforms. According to Castillo De Mesa and Gómez Jacinto (2022), better digital skills support stronger connectedness among social work graduates on social media platforms but do not guarantee a high levels of activism or large scale participation.

In addition, among all the four (4) statements in creativity, item 33 obtained the highest ($M=2.78$, $SD=0.68$) which described as moderately literate, indicates that students recognize their own creativity and often have fresh ideas but face difficulty applying them effectively in digital platforms. This suggests that while their creative thinking is strong, their confidence and practical skills in executing these ideas online needs improvement. In line of the study of Cojocariu and Boghian (2024) found that while many students demonstrate strong creative potential, they often lack the necessary digital confidence, resources, or guidance to express these ideas effectively online.

Whereas, item 30 got the lowest ($M=2.17$, $SD=0.71$) which described as slightly literate, indicates that students are rarely engage in online writing that showcases originality and personal perspectives. This result suggested that while students navigate digital tools, they often use them for consumption rather than creation. It is supported by the study of Manca and Ranieri (2017), which found that students tend to use digital tools passively, focusing more on interaction and information gathering rather than creative knowledge production.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=2.54$, $SD=0.80$) described as moderately literate of digital creativity. This result suggested that students are somewhat capable of expressing ideas online and engaging in creative digital activities such as posting content or developing multimedia outputs. However, their creative engagement remains limited, likely due to a lack of confidence or exposure to platforms that promote innovation and content creation. This is because while they have creative ideas, they may lack confidence, skills, or guidance in transforming these ideas into digital outputs such as blogs or videos. It is aligned in the study of Herawan et al. (2023) found that although students who search for learning materials, explore and encouraged to use digital tools tend to show better creative output. However, creativity is not yet at a very high level reflecting that many students are still developing confidence and exposure.

Furthermore, among all the three (3) statements in collaboration, item 36 got the highest ($M=3.05$, $SD=0.65$) which described as moderately literate, indicates that

students are comfortable collaborating with their peers in digital spaces to address academic tasks or solve shared challenges. This result aligns with previous research showing that digital collaboration supports students' problem-solving and learning outcomes. For instance, Wang and Wu (2022) demonstrated that online cooperative learning is significantly linked to higher problem-solving ability and satisfaction, while Jiang et al. (2023) found that online collaborative problem-solving is becoming a key skill in digital education. Further, Corrales and Tenorio (2024) showed that peer collaboration in online settings enhances cognitive skills such as decision-making.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=2.94$, $SD=0.71$) described as moderately literate of collaboration in online environments. This result suggested that most students are comfortable engaging with peers in virtual group work, sharing ideas, and solving problems collectively through digital platforms. This underscored the importance of teamwork and peer learning in achieving academic tasks efficiently in the digital world. This is because group activities and online teamwork are commonly used in academic tasks, allowing students to learn from peers and solve problems collaboratively. It is supported with the study of Kwiatkowska and Wiśniewska-Nogaj (2022) which found that students with higher digital skills are more likely to view online collaboration positively and benefit from peer learning. Moreover, Mena-Guacas et al. (2023) emphasized that students with strong digital competence exhibit higher levels of collaborative attitudes and performance across universities.

Finally, the overall mean of ($M=3.07$, $SD=0.79$) of levels of digital literacy of students described as moderately literate of digital literacy, showing that they can effectively use digital tools, locate reliable information, and apply digital skills in their learning activities. This suggest that most students are digitally capable and comfortable navigating online platforms, though there is still room for improvement in more advanced digital skills. This is because students possesses adequate digital literacy across all components, mainly due to regular academic exposure to technology. It corresponds to the study of Smith and Storrs (2023) which noted that students recognize the importance of digital literacy for academic and social purposes but still identify areas for improvement in their skills and confidence.

3. Students' Level of Digital Literacy Self-Efficacy Skills

As the independent variable of the study, the students' digital self-efficacy is being considered to determine their confidence and capability in performing digital tasks and to examine how their belief in managing, navigating, and adapting to digital environments influences their overall level of digital literacy.

Table 3 shows the students' level of digital self-efficacy in terms of cooperation in digital environments, emotion management in digital environments, information management in digital environments, and awareness in digital environments. Among all the seven (7) statements in cooperation in digital environments, item 1 got the highest ($M=3.47$, $SD=0.52$) which described as high, indicates that students are confident in communicating and interacting with others through digital platforms. This suggests that they are comfortable in expressing ideas, sharing information, and collaborating with

peers in online settings. It is supported by the study of Malabanan et al. (2022), which stated that students are generally confident in digital collaboration when provided with access to tools and clear objectives. Moreover, Olur and Ocak (2021) found that learners demonstrated strong self-efficacy in digital communication and teamwork when engaged in continuous online interaction and technology use.

Table 3
Level of Digital Self-Efficacy
n= 77

Components	Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Cooperation in Digital Environments	1. I am able to communicate with others in digital environments.	3.47	0.52	High
	2. I am able to collaborate with others in digital environments.	3.35	0.51	High
	3. I am able to share my knowledge in digital environments.	3.31	0.54	High
	4. I am able to ask others for the information I need in digital environments.	3.42	0.50	High
	5. I am able to assist individuals in digital environments who need information.	3.16	0.51	High
	6. I am able to create a new product in collaboration with others in digital environments.	2.70	0.74	High
	7. I am able to share a useful product I have created (e.g., video, article, etc.) in digital environments.	2.81	0.80	High
	Composite	3.17	0.66	High
Emotion Management in Digital Environments	8. I avoid displaying harmful behaviors towards others in digital environments.	3.64	0.48	Very High
	9. I respect to others while communicating in digital environments.	3.60	0.52	Very High
	10. I am not emotionally influenced by what I see or watch in digital environments.	3.03	0.69	High
	11. I am able to control my anger in digital environments.	3.48	0.53	High
	12. I am able to give positive reactions to things I enjoy in digital environments and express them.	3.44	0.53	High
	Composite	3.44	0.59	High
Information Management in Digital Environments	13. I am able to use search engines (Google, Yandex, etc.) efficiently.	3.65	0.48	Very High
	14. I am able to use the right keywords when searching on search engines (Google, Yandex, etc.).	3.43	0.57	High
	15. I am able to distinguish between relevant and irrelevant information in digital environments.	3.47	0.50	High
	16. I am able to summarize the information I access in digital environments by bringing it together.	3.32	0.52	High
	17. I am able to use the information I access in digital environments to achieve my goals.	3.36	0.54	High
	Composite	3.45	0.53	High
Awareness in Digital Environments	18. I am able to understand the positive and negative aspects of advertisements in digital environments.	3.44	0.57	High
	19. I am able to distinguish whether individuals are well-intentioned or ill-intentioned in digital environments.	3.26	0.57	High
	20. I am able to distinguish whether the information published in digital environments is true or false.	3.32	0.64	High
	21. I am able to defend myself against attacks from others in digital environments.	3.18	0.68	High
	Composite	3.30	0.62	High
Overall Mean		3.33	0.62	High

Statistical Tool: Weighted Mean

Legend: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA), 2.51-3.50 Agree (A), 1.51-2.50 Disagree (D), 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Whereas, the item 6 got the lowest (M=2.70, SD=0.74) described as high indicates that students are less confident in creating new products collaboratively in digital environments. This implies that while they can communicate and cooperate effectively, they still need more practice and guidance in digital content creation and project-based

collaboration. According to Pumprow and Brahm (2021) students with lower digital media self-efficacy tend to be less active in producing and sharing digital content.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.17$, $SD=0.66$) described as high means that students have high confidence in using digital tools to communicate, collaborate, share information, and work with others in digital environments. This result suggested that students are generally comfortable working with peers online, engaging in group tasks, and assisting others in digital spaces. This is because they frequently engage in group chats, online discussions, and collaborative academic tasks, which help them become comfortable working with others in digital spaces. It corresponds to the study of Malabanan et al. (2022) that students generally believe in their ability to work with others digitally, reinforcing opportunities and support such as access to digital tools, clear tasks, and guidance that would likely further boost their confidence and effectiveness. Moreover, this finding is guided by the “Self-Efficacy Theory” of Gallagher (2012) which claimed that an individual’s belief in their capacity to perform specific tasks develops through mastery experiences, social modeling, and positive reinforcement. In this context, students’ confidence in cooperating digitally reflects their growing experience and exposure to collaborative activities that strengthen their belief in their abilities.

In addition, among all the five (5) statements in emotion management in digital environments, item 8 got the highest ($M=3.64$, $SD=0.48$) which described as very high indicates that students consciously avoid displaying harmful behaviors toward others in online spaces. This suggests that they are mindful of their actions and aware of maintaining respect and positive behavior in digital communication. It is supported with the study of Steinert and Dennis (2022) which emphasized that understanding emotional affordances on social media enables users to regulate emotions and maintain digital well-being by avoiding harmful online interactions.

Whereas, the item 10 got the lowest ($M=3.03$, $SD=0.69$) which described as high, indicating that students are somewhat emotionally influenced by what they see or watch online. This implies that while students can generally control their emotions, they may still be affected by emotional or sensitive digital content. This finding corresponds with the study of Ibrahim et al. (2024), which revealed that emotional intelligence and digital literacy influence how students respond to online stressors, suggesting that greater emotional awareness leads to better regulation of reactions in digital contexts.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.44$, $SD=0.59$) described as high means that students are generally confident to manage their emotions effectively when engaging online. This result suggested that they are capable of expressing themselves appropriately, respecting others, and maintaining emotional balance in digital interactions. This may be due to their maturity and awareness of proper online behavior, allowing them to manage emotions, avoid conflicts, and communicate respectfully in digital environments. This finding aligned with Doménech et al. (2024) revealed that individuals with higher self-efficacy in emotion regulation tend to exhibit greater control over their emotional reactions and interpersonal behaviors. Thus, students are emotionally competent and capable of maintaining positive interactions in digital environments. However, the relatively lower score in resisting emotional influence from

online content implies that continuous guidance on emotional resilience and digital mindfulness may still be needed.

Moreover, among all the five (5) statements in information management in digital environments, item 13 got the highest ($M=3.65$, $SD=0.48$) which described as very high indicates that students are very confident in using search engines efficiently to locate relevant information. This suggests that students are skilled in navigating online platforms and utilizing digital tools for learning and research purposes. This finding is supported by Bacarrisas (2023) which found that students with higher self-efficacy in information literacy are more effective in retrieving and organizing digital information for academic use.

Meanwhile, item 16 obtained the lowest ($M=3.32$, $SD=0.52$) described as high, indicating that students are slightly less confident in summarizing the information they access in digital environments. This suggests that while they can gather information effectively, they may still face challenges in synthesizing or condensing it into meaningful summaries. This result aligns with the study of Daniel (2014) which found that learners with lower self-efficacy in information literacy tend to use digital resources less effectively but show willingness to improve through guided practice and training.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.45$, $SD=0.53$) described as high means that students are generally confident in managing and using information online. This result suggested that most students possessed an adequate skills in organizing, retrieving, and applying digital information effectively. This is because they regularly use search engines and online resources for research and academic requirements, enabling them to efficiently search, evaluate, and apply digital information. It corresponds to the study of Hatlevik et al. (2018) found that students who frequently use digital tools and search engines demonstrate higher information management self-efficacy, especially in retrieving and evaluating digital information. Moreover, Bacarrisas (2023) emphasized that students with high self-efficacy in information literacy tend to be more confident in conducting research and effectively using information resources that also reflects their competence in managing digital information.

Furthermore, among all the four (4) statements in awareness in digital environments, item 18 got the highest ($M=3.44$, $SD=0.57$) which described as high, indicates that students are aware of both the positive and negative aspects of digital advertisements. This suggests that they are developing the ability to think critically and recognize how digital content influences online behavior. According to Aldosari et al. (2020) digital citizenship awareness, including understanding online advertisements and content, is strongly linked to students' internet self-efficacy and responsible digital behavior.

Meanwhile, item 21 got the lowest ($M=3.18$, $SD=0.68$) also described as high, suggesting that students are less confident in defending themselves against online attacks or threats. This means that while students have a good level of awareness, they may still feel uncertain about managing digital risks and protecting their personal information. It is aligned in the study of Ma et al. (2025) which highlighted that although

students possess digital awareness, many still lack the confidence and readiness to handle cybersecurity challenges independently. Moreover, Scheel et al. (2022) emphasized that awareness alone is not enough; students must also build self-organization and independent learning abilities to strengthen their overall confidence in digital environments.

Hence, the overall mean of ($M=3.30$, $SD=0.62$) described as high means that students are generally confident in their awareness and confidence in recognizing credible information, digital threats, and online intentions. This result suggested that most of the students are aware of both the opportunities and risks present in the digital world. This is because they are aware of online risks, misleading information, and digital threats. This awareness may be attributed to their frequent exposure to digital media and discussions about online safety and responsibility. It corresponds to the study of Martens and Hobbs (2015) found that individuals with higher media and digital awareness are more capable of identifying persuasive strategies in online content, understanding advertising intent, and protecting themselves from misinformation and manipulation.

Finally, the overall mean of ($M=3.33$, $SD=0.62$) of levels of digital self-efficacy of students described as high means that students possess an effective level of digital self-efficacy, reflecting their confidence in using digital tools, solving online tasks, and managing learning activities in digital environments. This suggests that most students are self-assured and adaptive when engaging in technology-based learning. This is because students' strong exposure to digital tools in their academic activities has helped build confidence in using technology. This high digital self-efficacy supports their ability to engage effectively in digital learning environments. It corresponds to the study of Ansari (2022) that students with strong digital self-efficacy are more motivated and capable of adapting to online learning platforms, supporting the connection between confidence and digital success.

4. Difference in the Student Level of Digital Literacy and the Level of Digital Self-Efficacy When Grouped According to Their Profile.

As a comparative aspect of the study, this is being considered to determine whether students' digital literacy and digital self-efficacy differ significantly when grouped according to age, gender, and academic program and to identify if demographic factors influence variations in their digital competence and confidence.

Table 4 presents the significant difference in the level of digital literacy and the level of digital self-efficacy when grouped according to profile. No significant difference were found across age, gender, and academic program in terms of digital literacy. This suggest that students demonstrate a generally uniform level of digital skills regardless of demographic or educational background. This aligns in the study of A and Sinha (2022) which reported that students showed no significant differences in digital literacy by age. The study emphasized that exposure to digital learning environments across different age groups has led to more uniform digital skills. In addition, Lafifa and Rosana (2023) found no significant difference between male and female students. The results showed that both genders displayed comparable abilities in using digital tools and navigating online

information, suggesting that access to technology and learning opportunities has become more balanced. Moreover, the study by Jan (2018), which reported that students showed no significant differences in digital literacy across school levels or academic programs. The study emphasized that integration of digital tools and technology across various faculties has become more uniform, allowing students from different programs to develop relatively similar digital skills.

Table 4
Difference in the Student Level of Digital Literacy and the Level of Digital Self-Efficacy When Grouped According to their Profile
 n= 77

Student Level of Digital Literacy					
	χ^2	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	6.06	4	.194	Not Significant	Do not Reject H ₀
Gender	0.559	1	.455	Not Significant	Do not Reject H ₀
Program	1.80	2	.407	Not Significant	Do not Reject H ₀
Student Level of Digital Self-Efficacy					
	χ^2	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	9.71	4	.046	Significant	Reject H ₀
Gender	1.38	1	.240	Not Significant	Do not Reject H ₀
Program	3.96	2	.138	Not Significant	Do not Reject H ₀

Statistical Tool: Chi-square

On the other hand, results revealed that for digital self-efficacy, there is a significant difference when grouped according to age $\chi^2(4)=9.71$, $p=.046$ then, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that age influences students' confidence in using digital tools and performing online tasks. Older students tend to exhibit stronger self-efficacy because of greater exposure and experience in digital environments, while younger students may still be developing their confidence and skills in navigating online platforms. Thus, the claim of Ansari (2022) holds true to this result which says that older students showed significantly higher self-efficacy for online learning compared to younger students. It is supported by the study of O'Neill et al. (2024) that self-efficacy strongly influences older individuals' perspectives toward technology use, where greater confidence leads to higher engagement and reduced digital inequality. Thus, age plays a vital role in building confidence and competence in digital environments, as older students are often more goal-oriented and adaptable in managing online learning tasks.

Meanwhile, gender and academic program did not show significant differences, suggesting that both male and female students, as well as those from different academic programs, have relatively similar confidence levels in their digital abilities. This suggests that accessibility and familiarity with digital platforms may have become more uniform across students, regardless of their gender or chosen field. This finding is consistent with the study of Javier-Aliaga et al. (2024), found no significant gender differences in students' academic self-efficacy and digital competence. Their study emphasized that both male and female students now tend to possess comparable levels of digital skills, likely due to equal exposure to technology in academic and personal contexts. Similarly, the study by Sarva et al. (2023) found that students from different academic programs did

not significantly differ in their digital competence levels, indicating that digital readiness is now a shared attribute across disciplines.

Overall, these results highlight the need to support students, especially the younger students in building confidence with digital tools, while ensuring equitable access to digital resources to maintain uniform development of digital literacy across age, gender, and academic programs.

5. Relationship between the Levels of Digital Literacy of Students and Their Levels of Digital Self-Efficacy

As a correlational aspect of the study, this is being considered to examine how students' digital self-efficacy influences their digital literacy and to determine whether higher confidence in using digital tools and managing online tasks leads to stronger digital competence and performance.

Table 5
Relationship between the Levels of Digital Literacy of Students and Their Levels of Digital Self-Efficacy
n = 77

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation	Decision
Levels of Digital Literacy of Students and the Students' Levels of Digital Self-Efficacy	0.49	75	<.001	Significant	Reject Ho

Statistical Tool: Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC)

Table 5 revealed the relationship between the levels of digital literacy of students and their levels of digital self-efficacy using PPMCC. It indicates positive relationship between the levels of digital literacy and the levels of digital self-efficacy of the respondents, $r(75)=0.49$, $p<.001$. Hence the statement of the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the students' level of digital literacy is significantly influenced by their level of digital self-efficacy. This indicates that students who possessed higher levels of self-efficacy tend to have higher levels of digital literacy. In simple terms, when students believe in their ability to use technology effectively, they are more likely to explore, apply, and enhance their digital skills. Thus, the claim of Luginasin and Espinosa (2024) holds true to this result which says that self-efficacy strongly influenced students' engagement and personal growth, helping them take a more active role in their learning. It is supported by the study of Prior et al. (2016) revealed that higher self-efficacy is linked to stronger digital literacy and more confident participation in online learning activities. Moreover, Ervianti and Pratama (2024) also emphasized that students with higher computer self-efficacy are more capable of applying digital literacy in practical ways, from facilitating lessons to assisting peers in accessing and understanding information.

Further, this finding is supported by the Technology Acceptance Model of Davis (1989) which claimed that individuals are more likely to use technology if they find it easy

and useful, an idea closely tied to how confidence shapes digital literacy. Moreover, this result is guided by the Self-Efficacy Theory of Gallagher (2012) which highlighted that confidence can be developed through supportive experiences, showing that students' belief in their digital abilities can enhance both learning outcomes and future teaching performance. Thus, building students' confidence through hands-on digital experiences, guided practice, accessible technology, and supportive learning environments can lead to stronger digital literacy skills.

After a thorough analysis of the study, the researchers came up with the following findings.

1. Majority of the students were aged 21 (62.3%) and 22 (26%) years old, females (81.8%), and BTLEd-HE (46.8%) students.
2. The level of digital literacy of students in terms of communication (3.15 moderately literate), copyright (3.31 moderately literate), critical thinking (2.98 moderately literate), character (3.47 moderately literate), citizenship (3.66 highly literate), curation (3.21 moderately literate), connectedness (2.51 moderately literate), creativity (2.54 moderately literate), and collaboration (2.94 moderately literate) overall of (3.07 moderately literate).
3. The level of digital self-efficacy of students in terms of cooperation in digital environments (3.17 high), emotion management in digital environments (3.44 high), information management in digital environments (3.45 high), and awareness in digital environments (3.30 high) overall of (3.33 high).
4. There is a significant difference between the profiles of the students in terms of age to their level of digital self-efficacy, $\chi^2(4)=9.71$, $p=.046$.
5. There is a significant relationship between the levels of digital literacy of students and their levels of self-efficacy, $r(75)=0.49$, $p<.001$.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the thesis writers concluded that age, gender, and academic program do not significantly influence the digital literacy of pre-service teachers. Despite differences in these profile factors, students showed a high level of digital literacy, proving that they are skilled and capable of using digital tools effectively for learning. However, a slight variation was found in their digital self-efficacy when grouped by age, showing that older students tend to be more confident in using technology because of their experience and exposure. This study also revealed a strong relationship between digital literacy and digital self-efficacy, meaning that students who are more confident in their digital abilities also demonstrate stronger digital skills. Despite these positive results, the study also acknowledges several limitations such as time constraint of the respondents, as data collection was conducted during their regular academic schedules, which may have influenced the depth of their responses and the study was limited to only one campus, specifically BISU–Clarín Campus, which restricts the generalizability of the findings to other campuses or higher education institutions. Nevertheless, the study provides meaningful insights into the digital readiness of pre-service teachers and identifies areas that still need improvement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. The university may encourage more male students to enroll in education-related programs through career guidance activities, orientations, and advocacy programs. Moreover, students may also be encouraged to explore and enroll in other education programs, such as BEd and BEd-Math specializations, to promote balanced enrollment across academic programs.
2. Instructors and mentors may integrate more digital creativity activities such as blogging, digital storytelling, and reflective online writing tasks.
3. Instructors and mentors may provide more collaborative digital projects that require students to work together in producing shared outputs such as presentations, videos, or instructional materials.
4. Students may be provided with additional guidance, mentoring, and hands-on digital activities to help them build confidence in using digital tools. The university may continuously support programs that enhance both digital skills and confidence, such as regular digital skills training and technology-integrated instruction. Also, future researchers may conduct similar studies involving other campuses or variables to further validate and expand the findings of the present study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before the study commenced, the respondents received an informed consent form that detailed the study's purpose, scope, duration, and significance of their participation. This document served as proof that respondents had accepted the terms and conditions of the study. The study was conducted in strict adherence to fundamental ethical standards, with the researchers ensuring that all information collected was kept private and confidential, as outlined in the consent form. The respondents were informed about their involvement and their right to withdraw at any time. Access to the data collected from respondents was restricted to the researchers, respondents, and facilitators, guaranteeing complete confidentiality. Furthermore, the researchers were committed to maintaining the integrity and reliability of the study, ensuring that no data was falsified or manipulated in any manner, nor any information was added to or removed from the findings obtained.

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